

Credit Point Money Market Theory

ABSTRACT

Most of today's money market activities depend on interest rates. As long as interest rates are behind the wheel, it seems, world economy will be extremely sensitive to crises, and most of countries considering the economic concerns will not give enough importance of the level of welfare of citizens. It's time for the tired driver to change. We should give an opportunity for a new driver. In this study, we present a new theory "Credit Point Money Market Theory" with its driver, "Credit point", to pay for the rent of deposit money. Deposit money will gain credit points as to valid maturity rate in Credit Point System. Step by step, depending on credit point and maturity rate, many banking transactions will be defined and a new system will be constructed in the following pages.

Credit Point System supports savings and encourages solidarity. Currency and maturity will be as important as needed in Credit Point System. Depositor and debtor rights are carefully balanced. It is a system that carries the spirit of fair play for actors of both the players of money market and citizens. Because of this, it is suitable to human nature.

Key Words: Maturity rate, Credit point, Credit point market, Extra deposit

JEL CLASSIFICATION: D53 Financial Markets

INTRODUCTION

Throughout history, the struggle among those who defend interest and those who fight against has been continuous. Some concepts are:

Upon Plato, Laws, Book V :

“In marrying and giving in marriage, no one shall give or receive any dowry at all; and no one shall deposit money with another, whom he does not trust as a friend, nor shall he lend money upon interest; and the borrower should be under no obligation to repay either capital or interest.”

And upon Aristotle, Politics, Book I, Part 10:

“There are two sorts of wealth-getting, as I have said; one is a part of household management, the other is retail trade: the former necessary and honorable, while that which consists in exchange is justly censured; for it is unnatural, and a mode by which men gain from one another. The most hated sort, and with the greatest reason, is usury, which makes a gain out of money itself, and not from the natural object of it. For money was intended to be used in exchange, but not to increase at interest. And this term interest, which means the birth of money from money, is applied to the breeding of money because the offspring resembles the parent. Wherefore of any modes of getting wealth this is the most unnatural.”

Ancient Rome, strongly opposed to interest in splendor. However, the period of collapse it wrapped interest as a savior. Middle Ages, the church gave statements against interest and fought very seriously. The development of capitalism in the West, resistance against the interest completely loose and the interest has become a fact accepted by everyone. Today, despite ending resistance against interest, the peace did not come to humanity regardless of culture, religion and race. Nevertheless, interest has sustained acceptance in all societies even in Muslim world. There must be a reason for this. The biggest reason must be the lack of something better instead.

According to the capitalist idea, depositor should be awarded for transferring the using right of money. Capitalists have a consensus about accepting savings as a source of capital. Here are some of their assertions to justify interest:

- * A share of money should be given to depositor that, people get encouraged to economize.
- * Interest is a price for discouraging people from keeping the money in cash (liquidity preference)
- * Interest is the cost of a sacrifice. Consumer makes the savings by restricting food, beverages and clothing expenditures. This is a behavior that makes up the accumulation of capital.
- * Capital is productive and efficient. The benefit of the owner in the productivity of capital is quite normal. Interest has been paid off for his sacrifice.

Summarily, advocates say that the cost of hired money is a reality and it should be paid with money. So, the payment of interest is a right for depositor. There cannot be a rent of hired money is the basic argument of those who oppose interest. This argument did not prevent the spread of the interest. As a result of this, opponents of interest have defeated in the face of defenders.

It is a fact that the debtor uses the money for a maturity. This means depositor transfers using rights of money to debtor. In the past and today, not only depositors but also most of people think that money available now is worth more than the same amount in the future because of its potential earning capacity. To deny this is not a natural or logical, it is not fair too. Credit Point System neither denies the rent of hired money nor pays the rent with the money. Credit Point System pays the rent of money with credit point. To explain the system we need some definitions.

BASIC DEFINITIONS OF CREDIT POINT MONEY MARKET THEORY

Maturity rates

According to Credit Point Money Market Theory, shortly Credit Point System, since deposit money earns depending on time, time is the variable of money market. So deposit money or loans should gain maturity instead of interest. This new system suggests maturity rate bargain before money shopping. Investors gain time for rent of his money depending on valid maturity rate in money market.

The maturity rate of deposits: The ideal maturity rate of deposits is 100% in Credit Point System. 100 % means future days have almost same economic conditions for both depositor and debtor. There is no advantage to use money before or after. When maturity rate is 100%, depositors invest money with a maturity in order to get same maturity for same amount of money. But most of the time, a dollar one has today is worth more than a

dollar tomorrow. At those times, depositors will be reluctant to invest money for %100 and maturity rates will increase over %100 to find an equilibrium point. Deciding factor of maturity rates will be economical conditions like today. On the contrary, if the demand for money is lower, the rates will decrease under %100.

The maturity rate of a bank loan: It is a fact that banks sell money at a price better than the cost of funds. The maturity rates of bank loans are greater than the maturity rate of deposits so that banks earn money using the difference. Normally, maturity rates of bank loans should be greater than 100%. This means banks ask for longer time than rental period of the loan. As the demands for bank loans increase, maturity rates will increase up to 200%. We will use following abbreviations to calculate maturity rates:

T_d : maturity of deposit. T_o : maturity offered n : maturity rate

To find maturity rate we use following operation: $n = (T_o / T_d) \times 100$

Let's assume that bank A gives 60 days maturity to deposit money for 100 days. The maturity rate of the bank A can be found by $n = (60/100) = 60\%$.

60 % maturity rates of deposit means if you deposit money for 100 days (T_d) to the bank A, you will get back your money after 100 days and gain the right to use same amount of money for 60 days.

Let's assume that bank B wants 180 days maturity for a loan for 100 days. The maturity rate of the bank B can be found by $n = (180/100) = 180\%$.

180 % maturity rates of a bank loan means if you take up a loan for 100 days (T_d) from the bank, you will pay back your debt after 100 days and you owe using right of same amount of money for 180 days to the bank.

Let's assume that bank A declares 80 % maturity rate for deposits. This means if you invest money for 100 days (T_d) to the bank A, you will get back your money after 100 days and gain the right to use same amount of money for 80 days. $T_o = (80\% \times 100) = 80$ days.

Let's say that the bank B declared 150 % maturity rate for bank loan. This means if you get a loan from the bank B for 60 days (T_d) for example, you will pay back the money to the bank after 60 days and the bank will gain the right to use same amount of your money for 90 days. $T_o = (150\% \times 60) = 90$ days.

Credit point

In order to make gained maturity usable, we need a numerical value. It is Credit point. Credit point shows the cost of hired money. Credit points are the points that calculated for the rent of hired money. When maturity rate are not taken into account, "1 Credit point means 1-day rent of 1 unit money"

Using following abbreviations,

A: capital n : maturity rate t: time (days) p: credit point

We will calculate credit point by following operations: $p = (A \times n \times t) / 100$

Table 1 : Two credit point calculations are given in the following table

A: Capital	n : maturity rate	t: time (days)	$p = (A \times n \times t) / 100$
200\$	%50	60	$p = (200 \times 50 \times 60) : 100 = 6000$
500\$	%140	90	$p = (500 \times 140 \times 90) : 100 = 63\ 000$

Gained points can be remarked in many ways. For example, 6000p can be remarked as follows:

- 6000p shows "using right of 6\$ for 1000 days when maturity rate of loans is 100%"
- 6000p shows "using right of 60\$ for 100 days when maturity rate of loans is 100%"
- 6000p shows "using right of 600\$ for 10 days when maturity rate of loans is 100%"
- 6000p shows "using right of 6000\$ for 1 day when maturity rate of loans is 100%"
- 6000p shows "using right of 4800\$ for 1 day when maturity rate of loans is 80%"

In Credit point system, each dollars held in banks earn credit points depending on maturity rate and time (days). By giving points to each dollar, system supports savings of citizens, contributes to the accumulation of

capitals in the country. If someone keeps money in sight deposit in a bank instead of in pocket, he will use the advantage of gaining points. Following example is about this.

Example-1 :Let's assume that a bank applies maturity rate to sight deposit accounts. Mr. John keeps his money in this bank. The calculation of credit points of his money is following table.

Table 2 : The calculation of Mr. John 's gained credit points for his money in bank

Deposit(\$)	Days	(%)	Credit points
600	10	40	2400
450	12	42	2268
150	5	44	330
Total			4998

Mr. John can take up a loan from the bank without paying interest by spending gained credit points.

In a Credit point system, to use credit points, some owners want to take up a loan from the bank, some wants to save credit points in the bank for future use or to sell them to another, some wants to transfer gained points to another bank, some wants to borrow or to bequeath.

Credit points can be saved, spent, sold, transferred, borrowed and bequeathed in Credit Point System.

Calculating credit points makes it easy to:

- * keep the accounts.
- * find how much earnings.
- * compare money exchanges maturities and payment convenience.

Same as today, there will be many banks declaring different maturity rates in a Credit Point System. As a result of this, equal capitals will gain different amount of credit points for same days. Following example is about this issue.

Table 3 : The calculation of credit points of 600\$ at different maturity rates of different banks

A: Capital	n : maturity rate	t: time (days)	$p = (A \times n \times t) / 100$
600\$	Bank A %50	100	$p = (600 \times 50 \times 100) : 100 = 30\ 000$
600\$	Bank B %52	100	$p = (600 \times 52 \times 100) : 100 = 31\ 200$

Consumers may want to change their banks when at the time of spending of credit points. Credit point system allows consumers to transform points to other banks. Many ways can be found. Two ways may be as follows.

- Credit point market can be established for trading credit points.
- Credit points can be sold in stock exchange market.
- A coordinator body is set to declare a unique maturity rate for all banks.

Selling credit point in Credit point market

Credit points are the products of money in a Credit point system. It is a need to set a market for shopping credit points since credit points can be produced by different banks. After legal procedures, a Credit point market working with free market principles should be set. The products of this market are credit points. The consumers of this market are citizens, banks, companies, etc. The price of credit points in this market depends on demands and supply. Credit points exchange between banks is also an operation of this market. Those who don't have credit points can buy them in this market. Another important aspect of setting a Credit point market is that future earning for deposit money or the cost of a loan can be estimated by looking at the current price of credit point in the market. In addition to this, total amount of credit points in a country can be followed in this market.

Selling credit point in stock exchange market

The price of credit points will change depends on supply and demands like stocks. Also, different banks will produce different credit points in a Credit point system. So it will bring exchange problem between banks or people. To avoid this problem, every bank can sell its credit points in stock exchange market as to current price. This will cause an positive effect on economy.

Extra deposit

In a Credit Point system, a person who wants to use a loan but doesn't have credit point, either he may borrow credit points from the creditor or he may buy credit points in Credit point market. If the person borrows credit points, he must accept to make more payments after finishing the loan. In that case, the sum of more

payments is called Extra deposit. Extra deposits are given to debtor at the end of extra payments. Following example is about this.

Example -2: Mr. John wants to use 600 \$ bank loan for 90 days with maturity rate 180%. As to this maturity rate, he needs $(600 \times 180 \times 90) : 100 = 97200p$. He doesn't want to buy credit points in Credit point market. So, he prefers extra payments. As a result of payment plan signed with the bank,

According to agreement, he will pay back his debt to the bank after 90 days and he will make extra payments with 200\$ monthly. Since the payment is by installments, compound credit point calculation is done as in the following table:

Table 4 : Credit points calculation of Mr. John

Payments	Extra deposit (Total)	Days	Credit points $p = (A \times n \times t) : 100$
1.	200	30	6 000
2.	400	30	12 000
3.	600	30	18 000
4.	800	30	24 000
5.	1000	30	30 000
6.	1200	6	7200
Total			92 700p

As to the plan, he will pay 200\$ monthly .After 6 days later from 6th payment, he will get back his extra deposit (1200\$) from the bank. Hundreds of ways to pay for owed credit points can be found. Another one may be as follows:

Table 5: Another way for paying of Mr. John's 97 200p loan

Payments	Extra deposit (Total)	Days	Credit points $p = (A \times n \times t) : 100$
1.	400	20	8 000
2.	700	30	21 000
3.	1500	20	30 000
4.	1900	10	19 000
5.	1470	10	14700
Total			92 700p

Use of Credit points

Credit points can be saved in a bank account. Saved credit points provide many advantageous. First of all, saved points can be spent by taking up a loan from a bank. Next example is about it.

Example -3: Mr. John saved 120 000p in a bank. He wants to use 800 \$ bank loan for 100 days. Maturity rate of the bank loan is 160% . As to this maturity rate, he needs $(800 \times 160 \times 100) : 100 = 128 000p$. He wants to spend his saved points for this loan. After paying 120 000p, he owes 8000p. The bank offers a paying plan to him but he prefers to buy 8000p in Credit point market after 100 days.

Example -4: Mr. John hasn't got any credit point in a bank. He wants to use 600 \$ bank loan for 60 days. Maturity rate of the bank loan is 150% . He wants to pay the money with two installments. Since the payment is by installments, compound credit point calculation is done as in the following table:

Table 6: The calculation of credit points of 600\$ bank loan of Mr. John

Payments	Total	Days	Maturity rate for bank loan	Credit points $p = (A \times n \times t) : 100$
1.	300	30	150%	13 500
2.	600	30	150%	27 000
Total				40 500p

After paying 600\$, Mr. John has following ways to pay for credit points:

1. He may agree with the bank for an extra payment plan to pay for credit points. He will get back his extra deposit from the bank.

2. He may buy 40 500 points from Credit point market, someone or the bank as to current price.

Secondly, saved credit points can be sold to someone or in Credit point market. The price of credit points will be decided as to free and open market conditions. Depends on demands and supply, the price of credit points will increase or decrease. Some investors save credit points for the future use or for a better price. It is also a possibility for investors to save credit points for their children too. As a result, the system will have strong stability against crises.

According to Credit Point System, maturity rates of deposits and bank loans are determined by money market conditions. Those who have credit points and want to use;

- can spent points by taking up a bank loan as to current maturity rate.
- can sell points as to current fee in money market.
- can transfer points to another bank or person.
- can bequeath points.

Those who don't have enough credit points but want to take up a bank loan;

- can buy points as to current fee in money market.
- borrow points from someone.
- deal with an extra payment plan with creditor to pay for credit points, extra payment is rolled back.

Advantageous of Credit point system

Interest-bearing system with low interest rates makes a positive impact on development in a country, but it takes a very short time, such as a flash in the pan. Contrary to claims that the interest leads citizens to economize, it leads people to spend without accumulating. Today, almost 50% of citizens are debtor in Turkey. Moreover, in Interest-bearing system; the savings goes to the monopoly of a small minority. For example, 46,5 % of total deposit money in Turkey is belongs to 32 333 persons, according to 2011 data of Turkish Central Bank. Despite so many years of experience, Interest-bearing money system didn't start people to save money yet. Accumulations turned to get more interest rather than productive investments. Credit Point System has different perspective. It strongly supports accumulations for future spending or investments. "Save before spending." principle will be established by Credit point system.

Money increase in time deposits in a country in Interest-bearing system doesn't necessarily mean that there is an increase in accumulations in that country. By gaining interest for a maturity, money increases with time. To explain this, let's look at the following table.

Table 7 : Money Supply in Turkey at 14.01.2011

Date	Thousand TRY
M2	584 052 132
Time Deposits(TRY)	333 496 836
Time Deposits(FX)	123 589 559

Source: www.tcmb.gov.tr/yeni/evds/.../parabank/d_diger_pas.html

Let's consider that time deposits in Turkey won't change for next 6 months (no one invests money or no one take up a bank loan) and banks apply 5% interest rate for deposit accounts for 6 months maturity. After 6 months later, time deposits in banks will be as follows.

Table 8 : Estimated Money Supply in Turkey six months later from 14.01.2011

Date	14.01.2011 Thousand TRY	After 6 months Thousand TRY
M2	584 052 132	613 254 738,6
Time Deposits(TRY)	333 496 836	350 171 677,8
Time Deposits(FX)	123 589 559	129 769 036,95

According to table 8, it seems as if there is an increase in time deposits after 6 months later. Actually, the time deposits in bank haven't not increase but the figures have grown. This is a fictive growth, similar to snowflakes avalanches, can be a cause for crisis. In addition to this, banks can't hire all money in time deposit

accounts but pay interest for hired money and money that fail to rent. Let's look at the same situation if Turkey were in Credit point system.

Table 9 : Estimated Money Supply in Turkey six months later from 14.01.2011 (as to Credit points system)

Date	14.01.2011 Thousand TRY	After 6 months Thousand TRY	Credit points gains of depositors (Deposit maturity rate is %60)
M2	584 052 132	584 052 132	63 077 630 256
Time Deposits(TRY)	333 496 836	333 496 836	36 017 658 288
Time Deposits(FX)	123 589 559	123 589 559	13 347 672 372

If there were Credit point system in Turkey, the amount of deposited money would be same after 6 months later. This is natural and logical since money hasn't done anything during this time. Credit points in above table displays potential earnings of deposit money. After credit points are sold in Credit point market, or banks buy them from depositors,(That means someone will use the money), they turn into money.

Market conditions define the price of goods in a free and open market. No one can declare the price without presenting the product to the market. Similar to this, in Credit point system, the price of the product of money (That is, credit points) is determined after presenting it to the market. Although, Credit Point System allows investors to make calculations and guesses about how much they earn before investing money with a maturity, but future conditions in money market after maturity time and using method of credit points of the owner determine the factual earning. This is natural and healthy. On the other hand, in Interest-bearing system, the price of the product of money (interest) is determined before investment. Interest directly affects costs. It is not natural and healthy. It is clear that Credit Point System is more appropriate to free and open market conditions, human values such as social justice, natural life, environmentalism. Because of this, it doesn't bring any side effects along.

Credit points system brings the right to use money without interest to people. To get this right, people will be eager to save credit points by depositing money in banks. Without any cost, capital accumulation is accelerated. A few years later, the reduction of excessive consumption in the country and the concentration of productive investments are expected developments. As a result, better economic situation in the country is inevitable.

Extra deposit is a compulsory saving of debtor in Credit point system. Extra deposits will make great effect on accumulation in capital, on reducing inflation and excessive consumption in a country.

Today, some money owners wait for an increase of inflation rates, in crises generally, in the country to earn more money. After Credit Point System, the price of credit points will increase in stability because of growing desire to invest in production by using credit points, so they wait for stability to gain more money.

"For most of the 2000's capital has flowed from developing to developed countries. Table 6 below shows that net lending by developing to developed countries has been positive and rising after 2002. The figure lending derives from balancing out sources and uses of the available resources of each national economy. Negative net lending means that the national economy needs funds (from external sources) to cover its domestic expenditures; positive net lending means that the domestic economy is exporting national resources to the rest of world. This directly contradicts mainstream arguments regarding the desirability of international financial liberalization."

Source: Paineira, J.P. , Research on Money and Finance, Discussion Paper 4, 1979

Table 10: Net Lending – Sources and Uses of World Savings (% of GDP)

	Average 1994-2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007
Advanced Economies	-0.2	-0.7	-0.8	-0.7	-1.2	-1.4	-1.1
USA	-2.6	-4.2	-5.1	-5.5	-6	-5.9	-5.1
Japan	2.3	2.9	3.2	3.7	3.6	3.9	4.8
UK	-1.3	-1.6	-1.3	-1.6	-2.5	-3.9	-4.9
Euro Area	0.3	0.7	0.6	1.1	0.2	-0.2	-0.4
NI Asian economies	3.1	5	6.8	6.3	5.3	5.3	6.3
Emerging and developing economies	-0.7	1.2	1.9	2.4	4.1	4.8	4.2

Source: IMF 2008a

According to given table above, domestic economies in emerging and developing economies or NI Asian economies are exporting national resources to the rest of world. Great responsibility for this lending belongs to Interest-based system because of hot money. On the other hand, Credit point system will preserve domestic resources; prevent lending domestic capitals to outside. Because capitals will get credit points; need to be invested in production by someone to turn into money. Productive investments bring wealth to countries.

Conclusions

Living today or in the past, a lot of scientists expressed concerns about interest. Holy books definitely forbid it. In spite of great objections, Interest bearing system has been applied for centuries. As a result of applications, two drawbacks highlighted. First, money earns money without doing anything. Second, the interest of money is determined by interest rate before hiring. These two drawbacks caused to the impoverishment of the people, focus on the money to make money, to spend without saving, and so on. So why insist on the states in this system? One reason for this is the lack of a better system to replace for.

Credit point system eliminates these two drawbacks. Main thinking of Credit point system is to pay the rent of money with credit point so that the used money earns money, the earning of money is determined after maturity time as to current price of credit points in Credit point market. This thinking is natural, realistic and practical.

Primitive applications of Credit point system should be started in the state banks. According to the results of those applications, the authority can be given to other banks. Collected money in credit point system mustn't be used for gaining interest. Some states which forbid interest may be suitable for primitive application of this system. First application of this method can be in state funds. Since state loans are financed from taxes paid by citizens, it is not fair to give loans without any earning. Because of this, state loans to support farmers, artisans, etc. have to be started by using Credit point system. By making extra payments, debtors contribute the accumulation of money in the country; actually, it is a responsibility for all citizens.

Second application of this method can be started for encouraging saving by giving credit points to money held in banks. Since public money is the source of all economic activities in a country, accumulation of money and collection of taxes in the country will become easier and more efficient.

If we look at the Credit point system in terms of banks, it is perfect for the banks. Today, banks are focused to achieve high interest. Unfortunately, the banks try to make the citizen debtor in all life. The objective of the banks will be the development of citizen and country in Credit points system. However, the main responsibility of banks in Credit point system is to accumulate money for productive investment or the needs of citizens. The earnings of those banks will be credit points which emerge the difference between the maturity rate of deposit money and the maturity rate of bank loans. The responsibility for hiring money to someone in the bank will be the owner of money in this system.

It can be estimated that Credit Point System will cause following developments in economic and social life of a country:

- Lower sudden money movements in money markets.
- Reduction in the need for foreign resources.
- Establishment of new markets for trading Credit Points.
- Increase in productive investments.
- capital, knowledge and skills gain required importance
- A good change in people's social, economic, environmental and ecological perspective

LIMITATION OF THE STUDY AND FUTURE STUDIES

This research is theoretical. Ideas put forward by this study should be adequately discussed. Because it doesn't include selfishness and sordidness, people shall understand and accept Credit point system if necessary chance is given. State banks are suitable for primitive applications of the system. Legal infrastructures must be prepared and adopted by governments before applications. Application results will give the actual data about theory. Future research on banking with credit point is a large area. It can be done by cooperating with bank experts. But main philosophy of Credit Point System "Save before use" should be preserved like environment, nature and humanity.

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